

1 **Transcriptomics of HPV- and HPV+ head and neck cancer cell lines.**

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7 We hypothesized a cellular factor existed that authentically mediated some process that occurred
8 differently in cancers arising (or not) from high-risk HPV infection. We report here discovery of *Smc1b* as
9 an identifying transcriptional feature of HPV+ head and neck cancer cells.

10 Citations

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